

Non-oscillatory butterfly-type interpolation on triangular meshes

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Abstract

This paper proposes and analyses a non-oscillatory interpolatory subdivision scheme for data on regular triangular grids, a non-linear analogue of the well-known butterfly subdivision scheme. The scheme is obtained, first, by re-interpreting the butterfly refinement rule as a linear combination of ‘smaller’ linear rules and, then, by introducing a particular type of non-linear average in place of the linear ones. We end up with a non-linear interpolatory subdivision scheme that, applied to discrete data with large gradients, shows no Gibbs-like oscillatory phenomenon, while behaves similarly to the butterfly scheme when applied to smooth data. Convergence, reproduction and approximation properties of the proposed scheme are investigated and several numerical examples are discussed.

Keywords: Butterfly subdivision scheme, non-linear average, non-oscillatory interpolation.

2010 MSC: 41A25, 41A30, 65D05, 65D17

1. Introduction

The reconstruction of data with discontinuities across given curves or with sharp edges is an old and difficult problem that find applications in geophysical sciences, oil engineering, medical imaging and computer graphics, for example. The approximation of the data can be obtained via a two-stage process: First, a
5 detection algorithm is applied to localise the discontinuity, then a function is reconstructed by using a fitting method. But, it is well understood that smooth interpolants exclusively based on polynomials, splines or even radial basis functions become highly oscillatory near the discontinuities. To soften this phenomenon, there exists a number of papers developing different strategies like applying smoothing filters to the interpolant, post-processing techniques or locally adapted stencil selections (see the recent papers
10 [1, 2, 3, 4, 5] and references therein). Other approaches, not requiring the detection of the discontinuity, are based on non-linear subdivision schemes arising from non-linear averages, such as in [6, 7].

A considerable part of the literature deals with exact data placed on tensor product grids (as for the methods based on subdivision scheme, such as in [6, 7, 8]), or on triangular meshes but in a non-interpolatory

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setting [9]. Instead, our interest is in data interpolation on regular triangular grids, as for the butterfly
15 subdivision scheme, the starting point of our construction.

The *butterfly subdivision scheme*, BSS for short, is an iterative bivariate method for interpolating data on
triangular grids which can be interpreted as a recursive application of local cubic polynomial interpolation.
Essentially, the interpolatory subdivision recursion defines sequences of values on denser and denser triangular
20 meshes so that values on a given mesh are ‘copied’ at the same location on higher resolution levels, while
a local cubic polynomial interpolation followed by point evaluation is used to generate new data values. As
evident in Figure 1, the BSS inherits from polynomial interpolation a Gibbs-like oscillatory behaviour when
applied to discrete data with large gradients, a common situation in the numerical simulation of conservation
laws, for instance. This is due to the fact that evaluations of polynomials at a given point may produce data
with a large discrepancy with respect to the surrounding data.

25 To overcome this type of problems, several non-linear techniques have been considered in the literature, in
an attempt to construct subdivision schemes that avoid undesired oscillations. Examples of such schemes are
the renowned ENO-WENO subdivision schemes [10] or the PPH scheme [11]. The essentially non-oscillatory
(ENO) schemes, based on the pioneer work in [12], were a fundamental breakthrough in achieving both high
order accuracy in smooth regions, and non-oscillatory behaviour in discontinuity transitions. They are based
30 on an adaptive ‘stencil’ selection (i.e. points selection), according to the local smoothness of the underlying
function. The Weighted ENO schemes, based on the original research in [13], are improved versions of
the ENO schemes that perform convex combinations of approximations from different candidate stencils.
WENO schemes overcome some of the ENO shortcomings, such as instability, while maintaining the main
advantages. Even if ENO-WENO subdivision schemes manage to avoid the Gibbs-like oscillatory behaviour,
35 they rely on *smooth indicators* to select the proper rule, so these schemes could be also understood as 2-step
techniques. As an alternative that attempts to simplify the computations and to achieve a 1-step technique,
the use of non-linear averages in refinement rules has been studied in [11, 14, 15, 16, 17] in the univariate
situation, which effectively reduces the oscillations while maintaining low computational complexity and
stability. Later works successfully extended the idea to the non-oscillatory bivariate situation, such as
40 in [6, 7, 8, 9], but only for tensor product grids or in a non-interpolatory framework, to the best of our
knowledge. Note that, in univariate subdivision, non-linearity has been used also to design univariate
schemes that achieve properties like circle preservation or convexity preservation (see, e.g., [18, 19]).

In this paper we design and analyse a non-oscillatory BSS, a non-linear analogue of the butterfly in-
terpolatory scheme, where linear averages are judiciously replaced by non-linear averages that guarantee
45 a non-oscillatory behaviour of the resulting scheme. To this purpose, first we re-interpret the butterfly
scheme as a linear combination of ‘smaller’ linear schemes and then introduce the use of a particular type
of non-linear average. With this approach we end up with a non-linear interpolatory scheme for triangular

Figure 1: The left figure is a piecewise constant function where the red points and the black lines represent the initial data and the initial grid. Central and right figures are the interpolating functions obtained with 5 iterations of the butterfly and the non-oscillatory butterfly schemes, respectively, when starting with the red data also represented in the pictures.

grids that, applied to discrete data with large gradients, avoids the Gibbs-like oscillatory phenomenon with respect to the classical linear butterfly scheme while behaves similarly to the BSS when applied to smooth data.

The organisation of the paper is as follows: Section 2 is to provide preliminaries on subdivision schemes and non-linear averages needed to understand the non-linear, non-oscillatory butterfly scheme proposed in Section 3. The non-oscillatory behaviour of such non-linear scheme is discussed in Section 4 together with its polynomial reproduction capabilities and with some numerical examples. Convergence and accuracy of the non-oscillatory BSS scheme are investigated in Section 5 and in Section 6, respectively. Section 7 presents several numerical examples and a numerical discussion of stability while Section 8 discusses future work. The paper ends with an Appendix where the proofs of several technical and intermediate results are provided.

2. Preliminaries

This section is to introduce basic concepts concerning bivariate subdivision schemes, their reproduction capability, convergence, stability and approximation order. It also contains a short subsection that considers difference operators used in Section 5 and another subsection introducing the non-linear averages later used.

2.1. Basic definitions about bivariate subdivision schemes

We will follow a similar notation to [20]. For $\mathbb{N}_0 := \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ we consider the sequence of discrete sets of distinct vertices

$$\{\Xi^{(k)} := 2^{-k}\mathbb{Z}^2 \subset \mathbb{R}^2\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}_0}, \quad \text{such that} \quad \overline{\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \Xi^{(k)}} = \mathbb{R}^2.$$

In a general setting, a *stationary bivariate scalar subdivision scheme* \mathcal{S} is the repeated application of a *subdivision operator*, say S , that, at each *subdivision level* k , refines sequences of real values $\mathbf{f}^{(k)}$ attached to $\Xi^{(k)}$ thus yielding to sequences of real values $\mathbf{f}^{(k+1)}$ attached to $\Xi^{(k+1)}$. To simplify the subdivision description, since for all $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ there is a bijection between $\Xi^{(k)}$ and \mathbb{Z}^2 , we will consider subdivision operators always acting on $\ell(\mathbb{Z}^2)$, the set of real sequences $\mathbf{f} = [f_{\mathbf{j}} \in \mathbb{R}]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2}$, that is,

$$S : \ell(\mathbb{Z}^2) \longrightarrow \ell(\mathbb{Z}^2).$$

A standard assumption in applications is that every subdivision operator acts locally, i.e. for every $\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2$, there exists a finite ordered set of indices $\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{j}} \subset \mathbb{Z}^2$, called *stencil*, and a function

$$\Psi_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbb{R}^{n_{\mathbf{j}}} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad n_{\mathbf{j}} := \#\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{j}},$$

called *subdivision rule*, such that

$$f_{\mathbf{j}}^{(k+1)} = \Psi_{\mathbf{j}}\left(\mathbf{f}^{(k)}|_{\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{j}}}\right), \quad \forall \mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2. \quad (1)$$

Here, the restriction operator $\bullet|_{\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{j}}} : \ell(\mathbb{Z}^2) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_{\mathbf{j}}}$ is well defined because the stencil $\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{j}}$ is ordered.

We say that \mathcal{S} is *convergent* if, for every set of bounded initial data $\mathbf{f}^{(0)} \in \ell_{\infty}(\mathbb{Z}^2)$, the sequence of refined data converges to a continuous bounded function, here denoted as $S^{\infty}\mathbf{f}^{(0)} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, satisfying

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \sup_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2} \left| (S^{\infty}\mathbf{f}^{(0)})(2^{-k}\mathbf{j}) - \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{j}}^{(k)} \right| = 0.$$

With this setting, the classical BSS for the tri-directional grid [21] can be described as follows. For every $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2$, the stencils of the butterfly scheme are

$$\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{j}} = \begin{cases} \ell + \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\}, & \text{if } \mathbf{j} = 2\ell, \\ \ell + \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix} \right\}, & \text{if } \mathbf{j} = 2\ell + (1, 0) \text{ (horizontal stencil),} \\ \ell + \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix} \right\}, & \text{if } \mathbf{j} = 2\ell + (0, 1) \text{ (vertical stencil),} \\ \ell + \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \right\}, & \text{if } \mathbf{j} = 2\ell + (1, 1) \text{ (diagonal stencil).} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Since the butterfly scheme is *interpolatory*, for all $\mathbf{j} \in 2\mathbb{Z}^2$ the subdivision rule is the identity ($\Psi_{\mathbf{j}} = I$), otherwise the rule is

$$\Psi_{\mathbf{j}} : \quad \mathbb{R}^8 \quad \longrightarrow \quad \mathbb{R}$$

$$\mathbf{z} = [z_i]_{i=1,\dots,8} \longmapsto \sum_{i=1}^8 a_i z_i = \mathbf{z}^T \mathbf{a},$$

(where T denotes the matrix transposition) with

$$\mathbf{a} = [a_i]_{i=1}^8 = \left[\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{8}, \frac{1}{8}, -\frac{1}{16}, -\frac{1}{16}, -\frac{1}{16}, -\frac{1}{16} \right]^T, \quad (3)$$

and it is often referred to as the *insertion rule* of the scheme. Since in last expressions the explicit dependence on \mathbf{j} is only through $\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{j}}$, then the rule $\Psi_{\mathbf{j}}$ will be simply denoted as $\Psi_{\mathbf{B}}$. Therefore, the butterfly refinement at level k can be written as

$$f_{2\ell}^{(k+1)} = f_{\ell}^{(k)}, \quad f_{2\ell+\mathbf{d}}^{(k+1)} = \Psi_{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{f}^{(k)}|_{\mathcal{B}_{2\ell+\mathbf{d}}}), \quad \mathbf{d} \in \{(1,0), (1,1), (0,1)\}, \quad \ell \in \mathbb{Z}^2.$$

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The configurations for the horizontal, vertical and diagonal cases are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: From left to right: the configuration of the set $\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{j}}$ related to the horizontal, vertical and diagonal cases in (2), respectively. The cross indicates the position $\mathbf{j}/2$, while the bullets illustrate the elements of $\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{j}}$. The numbers are the corresponding coefficients of the mask (3).

The butterfly subdivision refinement described before consists in two different rules used at all subdivision levels: one for vertices already existing in the previous level (also known as *replacement rule*) and one for newly added vertices (also known as *insertion* or *refinement rule*). These rules are both linear rules and this is why the BSS is termed *linear*, where the vector \mathbf{a} defines the *mask*. Moreover, since at each level the set of points is preserved and included in the one generated at the next level, the butterfly scheme belong to the family of *interpolatory* subdivision schemes and it can be used to construct bivariate interpolatory functions on three-directional grids.

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Remark 2.1. We remark that the different stencils of the BSS could be obtained by using the ‘rotation’ matrix $R = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. Indeed, based on the notation

$$\mathbf{d}_{-1} := (1, 0), \quad \mathbf{d}_0 := (1, 1), \quad \mathbf{d}_1 := (0, 1), \quad D := \{\mathbf{d}_{-1}, \mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1\}, \quad (4)$$

we see that $\mathbf{d}_i = R^i \mathbf{d}_0$ for $i \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$, and that the stencils $\mathcal{B}_{2\ell+\mathbf{d}_i}$, can all be generated from $\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{d}_0}$, that we name simply as $\mathcal{B} := \mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{d}_0}$, by

$$\mathcal{B}_{2\ell+\mathbf{d}_i} = \ell + R^i \mathcal{B}, \quad i = -1, 0, 1.$$

2.2. Reproduction, stability and approximation order

We continue with recalling several useful definitions.

Definition 2.1. We say that a convergent subdivision scheme \mathcal{S} *reproduces* a set of functions $W \subset \{F : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\}$ if, and only if, for every $F \in W$,

$$\mathbf{f}^{(0)} = [F(\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2} \quad \Longrightarrow \quad S^\infty \mathbf{f}^{(0)} = F. \quad (5)$$

75 For instance, the BSS is able to reproduce polynomials with total degree up to 3 (e.g., see [22]).

A sufficient condition for reproduction is the so called *step-wise reproduction*, which is certainly easier to prove in practice. It is also a necessary condition for reproduction in the interpolatory case we consider.

Definition 2.2. We say that a subdivision scheme \mathcal{S} *step-wise reproduces* a set of functions W if, and only if,

$$S [F(2^{-k}\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2} = [F(2^{-k-1}\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2}, \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{N}_0, \quad \forall F \in W. \quad (6)$$

We continue with other important notions.

Definition 2.3. With the notation $g(h) = \mathcal{O}(h^r)$ we mean that there exists $M, h_0 > 0$ such that $|g(h)| \leq$
80 Mh^r for all $h \in (0, h_0)$. For a more detailed description, we may denote $g(h) = \mathcal{O}(h^r; p_1, p_2, \dots)$ when M or h_0 depend on some parameters p_1, p_2, \dots .

Definition 2.4. We say that a convergent subdivision scheme \mathcal{S} has *approximation order* r if, for any $F \in \mathcal{C}^r(\mathbb{R}^2)$, with bounded partial derivatives up to order r ,

$$\|S^\infty [F(h\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2} - F(h \cdot)\|_\infty = \mathcal{O}(h^r; F).$$

Definition 2.5. We say that a convergent subdivision scheme \mathcal{S} is *stable* if there exists some $M > 0$ such that

$$\|S^\infty \mathbf{f}^{(0)} - S^\infty \mathbf{g}^{(0)}\|_\infty \leq M \|\mathbf{f}^{(0)} - \mathbf{g}^{(0)}\|_\infty, \quad \forall \mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \mathbf{g}^{(0)} \in \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2),$$

where in the left part the usual infinity norm for bounded functions is used, while in the right part the infinity for bounded sequences, $\|\mathbf{f}\|_\infty := \sup_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2} |f_{\mathbf{j}}|$, is considered.

Definition 2.6. We say that a subdivision operator S is 1-homogeneous if

$$S(\lambda \mathbf{f}) = \lambda S(\mathbf{f}), \quad \forall \mathbf{f} \in \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2), \quad \lambda \neq 0.$$

2.3. Difference operators

For any two vectors $\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}' \in D$, with D as in (4), we define the *second order finite difference operator*

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} : \ell(\mathbb{Z}^2) \longrightarrow \ell(\mathbb{Z}^2) \quad [\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}} := f_{\mathbf{j}+\mathbf{d}+\mathbf{d}'} - (f_{\mathbf{j}+\mathbf{d}} + f_{\mathbf{j}+\mathbf{d}'}) + f_{\mathbf{j}}, \quad \mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2.$$

85 It satisfies $\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} = \nabla_{\mathbf{d}', \mathbf{d}}$, for all $\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}' \in D$.

Based on this operator, we define the vector-valued operator $\Delta : \ell(\mathbb{Z}^2) \longrightarrow \ell^6(\mathbb{Z}^2)$

$$\Delta \mathbf{f} := \left(\underbrace{\nabla_{\mathbf{d}_{-1}, \mathbf{d}_{-1}} \mathbf{f}}_{\Delta_1 \mathbf{f}}, \underbrace{\nabla_{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_0} \mathbf{f}}_{\Delta_2 \mathbf{f}}, \underbrace{\nabla_{\mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_1} \mathbf{f}}_{\Delta_3 \mathbf{f}}, \underbrace{\nabla_{\mathbf{d}_{-1}, \mathbf{d}_0} \mathbf{f}}_{\Delta_4 \mathbf{f}}, \underbrace{\nabla_{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1} \mathbf{f}}_{\Delta_5 \mathbf{f}}, \underbrace{\nabla_{\mathbf{d}_{-1}, \mathbf{d}_1} \mathbf{f}}_{\Delta_6 \mathbf{f}} \right)^T, \quad (7)$$

counting all possible distinct $\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'}$ that can be defined for different combinations of the directions $\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}' \in D$.

Note that, when dealing with data attached to the points in the stencil \mathcal{B} (shown in Figure 2-right), that is with $\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}}$, only 11 different finite differences values can be constructed. They are

$$\begin{aligned} & [\Delta_1 \mathbf{f}]_{(-1,0)}, [\Delta_1 \mathbf{f}]_{(0,1)}, [\Delta_2 \mathbf{f}]_{(0,-1)}, [\Delta_2 \mathbf{f}]_{(-1,0)}, [\Delta_3 \mathbf{f}]_{(0,-1)}, [\Delta_3 \mathbf{f}]_{(1,0)}, \\ & [\Delta_4 \mathbf{f}]_{(-1,0)}, [\Delta_4 \mathbf{f}]_{(0,0)}, [\Delta_5 \mathbf{f}]_{(0,-1)}, [\Delta_5 \mathbf{f}]_{(0,0)}, [\Delta_6 \mathbf{f}]_{(0,0)}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

It means that, given the 8 function values on \mathcal{B} , there are only 11 possible finite differences that can be constructed with the data.

We conclude this section recalling that the vector space $\ell_\infty^6(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ consists of vector sequences of type $\boldsymbol{\delta} = (\delta^i)_{i=1}^6 \in \ell_\infty^6(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ with $\delta^i \in \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2)$, whose infinity norm is defined as

$$\|\boldsymbol{\delta}\|_\infty = \max_{i=1, \dots, 6} \|\delta^i\|_\infty, \quad \text{where} \quad \|\delta^i\|_\infty = \sup_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2} |\delta_{\mathbf{j}}^i|.$$

2.4. Non-linear averages to design non-linear schemes

This subsection is to discuss the non-linear averages we use to define a non-linear but non-oscillatory version of the interpolatory BSS. Among the many known non-linear averages, relevant to our discussion are Lipschitz continuous non-linear averages that satisfy the following properties **P1**

$$\mathcal{A}(\alpha x, \alpha y) = \alpha \mathcal{A}(x, y), \quad \forall x, y, \alpha \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (9)$$

$$\min\{x, y\} \leq \mathcal{A}(x, y) \leq \max\{x, y\} \quad \forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (10)$$

$$\exists \tilde{c} \geq 1 : |\mathcal{A}(x, y)| \leq \tilde{c} \min\{|x|, |y|\}, \quad \forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (11)$$

We also consider averages that, in addition to **P1**, for fixed $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ and $p \geq 1$ satisfy the following **P2** properties,

$$|\mathcal{A}(x, y)| \leq |\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y|, \quad \forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (12)$$

$$\text{For each } x \neq 0, \quad |\mathcal{A}(x, x+h) - (\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)(x+h))| = \mathcal{O}(|h|^p; x). \quad (13)$$

Remark 2.2. The linear average $(x, y) \mapsto \lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y$ cannot fulfil (11). This is exactly why we consider non-linear averages. Observe that (11) also implies that $\mathcal{A}(x, y) = 0$ when $x \cdot y = 0$. Then, for $x = 0$,

$$|\mathcal{A}(0, h) - (1 - \lambda)h| = \mathcal{O}(|h|),$$

and this is why we exclude this case from (13). Note also that from (10) we deduced that

$$\mathcal{A}(x, x) = x, \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathcal{A}(x, y) > 0, \quad \forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}_+. \quad (15)$$

We also observe that, in addition to **P1** and **P2**, \mathcal{A} is required to be Lipschitz continuous in order to define a stable interpolation technique. At last, we mention that property (13) is crucial in the accuracy analysis.

Examples of Lipschitz continuous non-linear averages satisfying the conditions **P1** and **P2** are the Generalized Means GM_m , $m > 0$ (considered in [6] for $c = \sqrt[m]{2}$, $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$, $p = 2$), the Weighted Power- p mean $WH_{p,\lambda}$ (used in [23] for some c depending on p, λ) and the Power- p mean H_p (see [24] for the case $c = p$, $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$). The definition of the latter is recalled below as we will use it extensively:

$$H_p(x, y) = \frac{1}{2}(\text{sign}(x) + \text{sign}(y)) \left| \frac{x+y}{2} \right| \left(1 - \left| \frac{x-y}{x+y} \right|^p \right), \quad p \geq 1. \quad (16)$$

Here, we consider a simpler non-linear average based on two fixed independent parameters $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ and $c \geq 1$ defined as

$$A_{c,\lambda}(x, y) := \frac{1}{2}(\text{sign}(x) + \text{sign}(y)) \min\{|\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y|, c \cdot |x|, c \cdot |y|\} \quad (17)$$

and satisfying

$$A_{c,\lambda}(x, y) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x \cdot y \leq 0, \\ \lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y, & \text{if } x \cdot y > 0, \quad |\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y| \leq c \cdot \min\{|x|, |y|\}, \\ \text{sign}(x) c \cdot \min\{|x|, |y|\}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Remark 2.3. Note that, for any $\lambda \in (0, 1)$, $A_{1,\lambda}$ coincides with H_1 , also called the minmod average. In fact,

$$H_1(x, y) = \frac{1}{2}(\text{sign}(x) + \text{sign}(y)) \cdot \min\{|x|, |y|\} = A_{1,\lambda}(x, y). \quad (19)$$

⁹⁰ The next Proposition, whose proof is in the Appendix, discusses the properties of $A_{c,\lambda}$.

Proposition 2.1. *The two-parameter average $A_{c,\lambda}$ defined in (17) for $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ and $c > 1$ is Lipschitz continuous and fulfils properties **P1** and **P2** for any $p \geq 1$ and for any $\tilde{c} \geq c$.*

3. A non-oscillatory interpolatory subdivision scheme based on the BSS

In this section, we propose the construction of a non-oscillatory interpolatory subdivision scheme based on the BSS. This is done in two steps: first, we re-interpret the well known interpolatory BSS as an average of linear schemes. Then, we replace the linear averages by non-linear averages.

3.1. The refinement rule of the BSS

The reinterpretation of the refinement rule of the butterfly scheme, crucial for the definition of the non-linear scheme in Section 3.2, is inspired by the work done to define univariate, non-linear, non-oscillatory, subdivision schemes (see [14], for example). We already mentioned in subsection 2.1 that the butterfly refinement rule is a linear combination of values given at 8 surrounding vertices around the vertex where we want to insert a value in the triangular grid. With the notation of Figure 3, it reads as

$$\Psi_B(\mathbf{z}) = \frac{1}{2}(z_1 + z_2) + \frac{1}{8}(z_3 + z_4) - \frac{1}{16}(z_6 + z_5 + z_7 + z_8), \quad \mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^8. \quad (20)$$

Note that the coefficients and the vertex location are the same for all the orientations which justifies the use of the butterfly scheme even for general triangular meshes.

Figure 3: Left: the topological configuration of the vertices around the vertex where a new value need to be inserted, where labels are ordered as in the definition of \mathcal{B} , in (2). Right: the coefficients values of the butterfly rule associated to each data.

The butterfly refinement rule in (20) can be obtained in several different ways. The original deduction was done in [21], based on the extension of the univariate four point scheme [25] to the bivariate scenario. Another way to derive (20) is via bivariate third degree polynomial interpolation: Given the 8 values depicted into Figure 3-left, an interpolating cubic polynomial is built and the new value to be inserted is obtained by polynomial evaluation at the corresponding location. This interpretation makes very easy to understand the reproduction of Π_3 which characterises the butterfly scheme [26]. In this paper, we explore an alternative approach to obtain the butterfly coefficients: We construct four quadratic polynomials interpolating at 6 points, evaluate them at the cross point ‘x’, and then average the result. It is not difficult to check that the 4 different configurations of points represented in Figure 4 as ‘•’ are unisolvent point sets, hence each of them identify a unique quadratic interpolant polynomial. Therefore, the evaluation of the four quadratic polynomials interpolating the point sets of Figure 4 at the cross point ‘x’ defines 4 refinement rules (whose coefficients are also depicted in Figure 4). We name them as the *north*, *south*, *west* and *east* rules and denote them by $\Psi_N, \Psi_S, \Psi_W, \Psi_E$, respectively. Note that, by construction, each of these rules reproduces Π_2 and therefore any convex combination of them also reproduce Π_2 . Note also that in the north and south rules a coefficient is zero, meaning that the corresponding refinement rules are based on 5 points only. They are,

Figure 4: The four possible configurations of points used to generate interpolating quadratic polynomials.

for $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^8$,

$$\Psi_N(\mathbf{z}) = \frac{1}{2}(z_1 + z_2) - \frac{1}{8}(z_6 - 2z_4 + z_5), \quad \Psi_W(\mathbf{z}) = \frac{3}{4}z_1 + \frac{1}{4}z_2 + \frac{1}{8}(z_4 - z_6 + z_3 - z_7),$$

$$\Psi_S(\mathbf{z}) = \frac{1}{2}(z_1 + z_2) - \frac{1}{8}(z_7 - 2z_3 + z_8), \quad \Psi_E(\mathbf{z}) = \frac{1}{4}z_1 + \frac{3}{4}z_2 + \frac{1}{8}(z_4 - z_5 + z_3 - z_8),$$

from which we see that the refinement rule of the butterfly scheme Ψ_B can be seen in two different ways

$$\Psi_B = \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_N + \Psi_S), \quad \text{or} \quad \Psi_B = \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_W + \Psi_E). \quad (21)$$

Therefore, for any non-linear average \mathcal{A} such that $\mathcal{A}(x, x) = x$, Ψ_B can also be written as

$$\Psi_B = \mathcal{A}\left(\frac{1}{2}\Psi_N + \frac{1}{2}\Psi_S, \frac{1}{2}\Psi_W + \frac{1}{2}\Psi_E\right).$$

Moreover, if we consider a ‘kernel’ interpolatory subdivision scheme with refinement rule Ψ_K , the refinement rule of the BSS can be written as

$$\Psi_B = \Psi_K + \mathcal{A}\left(\frac{1}{2}(\Psi_N - \Psi_K) + \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_S - \Psi_K), \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_W - \Psi_K) + \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_E - \Psi_K)\right), \quad (22)$$

100 which is the starting point of our non-linear construction.

The kernel scheme is introduced with two aims: The first one is to provide a non-oscillatory rule in presence of a discontinuity and the second one is to grant a reference scheme to detect, by comparison, if the north, south, east and west rules produce oscillations. As kernel scheme we propose the use of the linear interpolatory subdivision scheme associated with the three-direction box spline $B_{1,1,1}$ [27] whose insertion rule is

$$\Psi_K(\mathbf{z}) = \frac{1}{2}(z_1 + z_2). \quad (23)$$

With this selection of Ψ_K , the differences appearing in (22) are second order finite differences:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_N(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_K(\mathbf{z}) &= -\frac{1}{8}(z_6 - 2z_4 + z_5), \\ \Psi_S(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_K(\mathbf{z}) &= -\frac{1}{8}(z_7 - 2z_3 + z_8), \\ \Psi_W(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_K(\mathbf{z}) &= \frac{1}{8}(z_1 - z_2 - z_6 + z_4) - \frac{1}{8}(z_7 - z_3 - z_1 + z_2), \\ \Psi_E(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_K(\mathbf{z}) &= \frac{1}{8}(z_3 - z_8 - z_1 + z_2) - \frac{1}{8}(z_1 - z_2 - z_4 + z_5). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Hence, for data attached to \mathcal{B} we define the difference operator $\Delta^{\mathcal{B}} : \mathbb{R}^8 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^6$ with components

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_1 &:= z_7 - 2z_3 + z_8, & [\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_2 &:= z_6 - 2z_4 + z_5, & [\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_3 &:= z_1 - z_2 - z_6 + z_4, \\ [\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_4 &:= z_3 - z_8 - z_1 + z_2, & [\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_5 &:= z_7 - z_1 - z_3 + z_2, & [\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_6 &:= z_1 - z_2 - z_4 + z_5, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

so that the differences in (24) can be denoted by

$$\Psi_{\text{N}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}) = -\frac{1}{8}[\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_2, \quad \Psi_{\text{W}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}) = \frac{1}{8}[\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_3 - \frac{1}{8}[\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_5, \quad (26)$$

$$\Psi_{\text{S}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}) = -\frac{1}{8}[\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_1, \quad \Psi_{\text{E}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}) = \frac{1}{8}[\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_4 - \frac{1}{8}[\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_6. \quad (27)$$

Therefore, we can further express all differences in (24) as the composition of the four operators

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}_{\text{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\text{S}}, \mathcal{G}_{\text{W}}, \mathcal{G}_{\text{E}} &: \mathbb{R}^6 \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ \mathcal{G}_{\text{N}}(\mathbf{w}) &:= -\frac{1}{8}w_2, \quad \mathcal{G}_{\text{S}}(\mathbf{w}) := -\frac{1}{8}w_1, \quad \mathcal{G}_{\text{W}}(\mathbf{w}) := \frac{1}{8}w_3 - \frac{1}{8}w_5, \quad \mathcal{G}_{\text{E}}(\mathbf{w}) := \frac{1}{8}w_4 - \frac{1}{8}w_6, \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where $\mathbf{w} = (w_1, \dots, w_6)$, with the difference operator $\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}$, that is as

$$\Psi_{\text{C}} - \Psi_{\text{K}} = \mathcal{G}_{\text{C}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}}, \quad \text{C} \in \{\text{N}, \text{S}, \text{W}, \text{E}\}. \quad (29)$$

In conclusion, defining the non-linear operator \mathcal{G}_{B}

$$\mathcal{G}_{\text{B}} := \mathcal{A} \left(\frac{1}{2}\mathcal{G}_{\text{N}} + \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{G}_{\text{S}}, \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{G}_{\text{W}} + \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{G}_{\text{E}} \right),$$

we are able to express the refinement rule of the Butterfly scheme in terms of a non-linear operator combined with second order finite differences as

$$\Psi_{\text{B}} = \Psi_{\text{K}} + \mathcal{G}_{\text{B}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}}. \quad (30)$$

From (20) and (23) we deduce that for $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{Z}^8$

$$\Psi_{\text{B}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}) = -\frac{1}{16}(z_6 - 2z_4 + z_5) - \frac{1}{16}(z_7 - 2z_3 + z_8) = -\frac{1}{16}[\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_1 - \frac{1}{16}[\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_2, \quad (31)$$

which implies that, for $\|\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})\|_{\infty} = \max_{i=1, \dots, 6} \{ |[\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})]_i| \}$ and for $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^8$,

$$|\Psi_{\text{B}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})| \leq \frac{1}{8} \|\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})\|_{\infty}, \quad (32)$$

and therefore that

$$|(\mathcal{G}_{\text{B}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})| \leq \frac{1}{8} \|\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})\|_{\infty}. \quad (33)$$

3.2. A non-oscillatory refinement rule

Unfortunately, each of the rules $\Psi_{\text{N}}, \Psi_{\text{S}}, \Psi_{\text{W}}, \Psi_{\text{E}}$ represented in Figure 5 produces oscillations when involving data with large gradients. Suppose that the jump (or the discontinuity) is along the continuous red line as in Figure 5-(a). In that situation, only the north rule uses data at the same side of the jump

and hence, the latter is the most convenient refinement rule to use. Similarly, the south, east and west rules would be suitable when the jump is as represented in Figure 5-(b),5-(c) and 5-(d), respectively. The problem is that the identification of the discontinuity location is a quite complicated task (see [8], for example), and it is usually reached within a cell average framework rather than an interpolatory one. Therefore, our idea is to start from (22) where the kernel scheme is a non-oscillatory linear subdivision scheme, and then replace the linear averages in (22) by non-linear averages that are known to guarantee a non-oscillatory behaviour. In other words, based on three non-linear Lipschitz continuous averages, say \mathcal{A} , $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$, $\hat{\mathcal{A}}$, we propose the non-linear refinement rule acting on $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^8$ as

$$\Psi_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{z}) := \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}) + \mathcal{A} \left(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}(\Psi_{\text{N}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}), \Psi_{\text{S}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})), \hat{\mathcal{A}}(\Psi_{\text{W}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}), \Psi_{\text{E}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})) \right), \quad (34)$$

with \mathcal{A} satisfying properties **P1** and $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}, \hat{\mathcal{A}}$ satisfying properties **P1** and **P2** with $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$. Specifically, as non-linear average \mathcal{A} we use H_1 , the *minmod* average in (19), while we set $\tilde{\mathcal{A}} = \hat{\mathcal{A}} = A_{\frac{4}{3}, \frac{1}{2}}$ with $A_{\frac{4}{3}, \frac{1}{2}}$ as defined in (17). This particular choice of the non-linear averages is motivated by numerical evidences, shown in Section 7. For shortness, we omit the dependence on $\frac{4}{3}, \frac{1}{2}$ in $A_{\frac{4}{3}, \frac{1}{2}}$ and denote the non-linear average simply as A , arriving at

$$\Psi_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{z}) := \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}) + H_1(A(\Psi_{\text{N}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}), \Psi_{\text{S}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})), A(\Psi_{\text{W}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}), \Psi_{\text{E}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}))). \quad (35)$$

Base on (23) and (24), a more explicit expression of Ψ_{NB} , is

$$\Psi_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{z}) := \frac{1}{2}(z_1 + z_2) - \frac{1}{8}H_1(A(z_5 - 2z_4 + z_6, z_7 - 2z_3 + z_8), A(z_6 + z_7 - z_3 - z_4, z_5 + z_8 - z_3 - z_4)). \quad (36)$$

The eight stencil values (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_8) are distributed around the middle point of the edge (the cross in Figure 3), where the new value is going to be inserted. Based on (36) and the usual grid refinement of the butterfly scheme [21], the proposed scheme can be easily implemented.

105 *Remark 3.1.* We remark that the choice $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$ is motivated by the purpose of being as close as possible to the BSS while the choice $c = \frac{4}{3}$, as well as the choice of H_1 , is motivated by numerical properties of the non-oscillatory scheme discussed in Section 7.

Following the same lines of reasoning as in the butterfly case, we express the non-linear rule in terms of second order finite differences as

$$\Psi_{\text{NB}} = \Psi_{\text{K}} + \mathcal{G}_{\text{NB}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}}, \quad \text{where} \quad \mathcal{G}_{\text{NB}} := H_1(A(\mathcal{G}_{\text{N}}, \mathcal{G}_{\text{S}}), A(\mathcal{G}_{\text{W}}, \mathcal{G}_{\text{E}})). \quad (37)$$

Due to (10) (for H_1) and (12) (with $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$) for $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ we have

$$|\mathcal{G}_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{w})| \leq \max\{|A(\mathcal{G}_{\text{N}}(\mathbf{w}), \mathcal{G}_{\text{S}}(\mathbf{w}))|, |A(\mathcal{G}_{\text{W}}(\mathbf{w}), \mathcal{G}_{\text{E}}(\mathbf{w}))|\} \quad (38)$$

$$\leq \max\left\{\left|\frac{1}{2}\mathcal{G}_{\text{N}}(\mathbf{w}) + \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{G}_{\text{S}}(\mathbf{w})\right|, \left|\frac{1}{2}\mathcal{G}_{\text{W}}(\mathbf{w}) + \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{G}_{\text{E}}(\mathbf{w})\right|\right\}, \quad (39)$$

Figure 5: From left to right: the four masks corresponding to the north, south, west and east schemes. Each red lines symbolizes a discontinuity in the data.

that, together with (37), (29) and (21), gives for $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^8$

$$\begin{aligned}
|\Psi_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})| &= |(\mathcal{G}_{\text{NB}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})| \\
&\leq \max \left\{ \left| \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{\text{N}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})) + \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{\text{S}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})) \right|, \left| \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{\text{W}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})) + \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{\text{E}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})) \right| \right\} \\
&= \max\{|\Psi_{\text{B}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})|, |\Psi_{\text{B}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})|\} = |\Psi_{\text{B}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})|.
\end{aligned}$$

Finally, we use (32) to deduced that

$$|\Psi_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{z}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z})| = |(\mathcal{G}_{\text{NB}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})| \leq \frac{1}{8} \|\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{z})\|_{\infty}, \quad \mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^8, \quad (40)$$

which is the non-linear counterpart of (33).

4. The non-oscillatory BSS and its properties

With the refinement rule in (35) the interpolatory, non-linear, non-oscillatory, subdivision scheme we propose is based on the rules

$$f_{2\ell}^{(k+1)} = f_{\ell}^{(k)}, \quad f_{2\ell+d_i}^{(k+1)} = \Psi_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{f}^{(k)}|_{\mathcal{B}_{2\ell+d_i}}), \quad i = -1, 0, 1, \quad \ell \in \mathbb{Z}^2, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0. \quad (41)$$

110 The corresponding subdivision operator is denoted as S_{NB} , and the associate subdivision scheme denoted as \mathcal{S}_{NB} , is named *non-oscillatory butterfly subdivision scheme* or NOBSS, for shortness. Below, we investigate the behaviour of the NOBSS when applied to data with discontinuities as well as its polynomial reproduction capabilities. Convergence and approximation order –that is, the behaviour when applied to smooth data– will be discussed in Section 5.

115 4.1. Analysis of the behaviour when applied to data with discontinuities

In this section we assume that the data, $\mathbf{f} \in \ell(\mathbb{Z}^2)$, comes from a piecewise smooth function F , that is $f_{\mathbf{j}} = F(h\mathbf{j})$, $\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2$, $h > 0$. We assume that F is smooth everywhere except along a given curve, say Γ ,

where either F or its first partial derivatives have a jump discontinuity. The second type of discontinuity is often called an *edge* of the function F . Taking into consideration that the scheme is applied locally, and that the smaller is h the closer Γ is locally to its tangent, we assume that Γ is a straight line to simplify the discussion. Obviously, Γ divides the plane in two parts, let say Γ_- and Γ_+ , so that $\mathbb{R}^2 = \Gamma_- \cup \Gamma_+ \cup \Gamma$.

For a fixed $\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \setminus 2\mathbb{Z}^2$, let us analyse the value $\Psi_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j})$ that the scheme uses to approximate $F(h\mathbf{j}/2)$ when Γ crosses \mathcal{B}_j so that some stencil values belong to Γ_+ while the rest belong to Γ_- . For instance, Figure 5-(a) represents the situation where only z_7, z_3 belong to Γ_+ . The refinement rules Ψ_{N} and Ψ_{K} only uses smooth data and, since they respectively have approximation order 3 and 2 (see Lemma 6.1 in the Appendix), we can write

$$\Psi_{\text{N}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = F(h\mathbf{j}/2) + \mathcal{O}(h^3; F), \quad \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = F(h\mathbf{j}/2) + \mathcal{O}(h^2; F).$$

Therefore,

$$\Psi_{\text{N}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = \mathcal{O}(h^2; F). \quad (42)$$

Note that the \mathcal{O} -expressions in this section depend on F , we omit it for the sake of shortness from now on. On the contrary, $\Psi_{\text{S}}, \Psi_{\text{W}}$ and Ψ_{E} use data belonging to both Γ_+ and Γ_- . Since they are based on polynomial interpolation, they have an interpolation error of the same magnitude as the discontinuity jump. Denoting the jump value by $\mathcal{O}(h^s)$, with $s = 0$, in case the jump is in F , and with $s = 1$, in case the jump is in the first partial derivatives, we have

$$\Psi_{\text{S}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = F(h\mathbf{j}/2) + \mathcal{O}(h^s), \quad \Psi_{\text{W}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = F(h\mathbf{j}/2) + \mathcal{O}(h^s), \quad \Psi_{\text{E}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = F(h\mathbf{j}/2) + \mathcal{O}(h^s).$$

Hence,

$$\Psi_{\text{S}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = \mathcal{O}(h^s), \quad \Psi_{\text{W}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = \mathcal{O}(h^s), \quad \Psi_{\text{E}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = \mathcal{O}(h^s).$$

Since property (11) of the non-linear averages implies that

$$A(\mathcal{O}(h^r), \mathcal{O}(h^s)) = \mathcal{O}(h^{\max\{r,s\}}),$$

we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} A(\Psi_{\text{N}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}), \Psi_{\text{S}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j})) &= A(\mathcal{O}(h^2), \mathcal{O}(h^s)) = \mathcal{O}(h^2), \\ A(\Psi_{\text{W}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}), \Psi_{\text{E}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) - \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j})) &= A(\mathcal{O}(h^s), \mathcal{O}(h^s)) = \mathcal{O}(h^s). \end{aligned}$$

In conclusion,

$$\Psi_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) + \text{H}_1(\mathcal{O}(h^2), \mathcal{O}(h^s)) = F(h\mathbf{j}/2) + \mathcal{O}(h^2),$$

showing the non-oscillatory behaviour of the non-linear butterfly refinement rule in presence of discontinuous data. In a similar way we can treat the other possible configurations of Γ illustrated in Figure 5 and conclude that in all these Γ configurations, the non-oscillatory butterfly has second order of approximation.

125 There is only one configuration of Γ not considered in Figure 5, that is when Γ is separating z_1 and z_2 .
 Since we are working in the interpolatory framework, it is not possible to detect if the discontinuity is nearer
 to z_1 than to z_2 , or vice-versa, and we cannot expect an accurate prediction of F at \times . By (35), the value
 we assign is $\Psi_K(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j})$ plus a non-linear average of the four differences $\Psi_C(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) - \Psi_K(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j})$, $C \in \{N,S,W,E\}$.
 In this situation, the differences have different sign, and the non-linear average returns zero due to (17).
 130 Hence, the non-linear rule coincides with the kernel rule.

4.2. Polynomial reproduction

Proposition 4.1. *The NOBSS, based on the refinement rule (35), reproduces Π_2 .*

Proof. Since the scheme is interpolatory, it is sufficient to check the step-wise reproduction, which consists
 in checking that $\Psi_{NB}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = F(\mathbf{j}/2)$ when $\mathbf{f} = [F(h\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2}$, $F \in \Pi_2$, $\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \setminus 2\mathbb{Z}^2$. Since all the rules
 $\Psi_N, \Psi_S, \Psi_W, \Psi_E$ reproduces Π_2 by construction, then

$$F(\mathbf{j}/2) - \Psi_K(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = \Psi_C(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) - \Psi_K(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}), \quad C \in \{N,S,W,E\}.$$

Due to (14), that is to the property $H_1(x, x) = x$ and $A(x, x) = x$, with $x := F(\mathbf{j}/2) - \Psi_K(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j})$, we conclude

$$\Psi_{NB}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) = \Psi_K(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) + H_1(A(x, x), A(x, x)) = \Psi_K(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_j}) + x = F(\mathbf{j}/2),$$

which is the quadratic polynomial reproduction property of the non-oscillatory butterfly scheme. \square

Remark 4.1. We remark that Π_2 -reproduction is guaranteed for any choice in (34) of $\mathcal{A}, \tilde{\mathcal{A}}, \hat{\mathcal{A}}$ fulfilling (14).

135 4.3. Numerical examples

This subsection is to display several pictures comparing the BSS and the NOBSS interpolants applied
 to data on triangular grids that underline the non-oscillatory behaviour of the latter. We consider three
 different piecewise smooth functions:

$$F(x, y) = \begin{cases} x + y - 1, & x > \max\{\frac{1}{2}, y\}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (x, y) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1], \quad (43)$$

$$F(x, y) = \frac{3 \cos\left(\frac{(10x-5)^2 + (10y-5)^2}{3}\right)}{3 + (10x-5)^2 + (10y-5)^2} + \begin{cases} 10 - 20(y - \frac{1}{2})^2, & x > \frac{1}{2}, \\ 0, & x \leq \frac{1}{2}, \end{cases} \quad (x, y) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1], \quad (44)$$

$$F(x, y) = \arctan\left(100 \left(\sqrt{\left(x - \frac{3}{2}\right)^2 + y^2} - \frac{\pi}{3}\right)\right), \quad (x, y) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1]. \quad (45)$$

The first one, (43), is a piecewise-linear function with a discontinuity along two lines that join at a corner;
 the second one, (44), is a shifted version of the function test proposed in [6, section 5], with a discontinuity

along the line $x = \frac{1}{2}$; The last one, (45), is a continuous function with large gradient in the neighbourhood of the conic section $(x - \frac{3}{2})^2 + y^2 = \frac{\pi^2}{9}$. The graphs of these functions are illustrated in the left of Figures 6, 7 and 9, respectively. The first two functions are evaluated at the points of a uniform triangular grid with vertices $\{\frac{1}{N}(i, j)\}_{i,j=0}^{14}$, while the last function is evaluated at a non-uniform triangular grid with vertices

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{N} (i + 0.3(\cos(i) + \sin(j)), j + 0.3(\sin(i) + \cos(j))) \right\}_{i,j=0}^{14}.$$

Figure 6: Top row: The left figure is the function (43) where the red points and the black lines represent the initial data and the initial grid. The central and right figures are the refined data obtained with 5 iterations of the butterfly and the non-oscillatory butterfly schemes, respectively, when starting with the red data represented in the pictures. Bottom row: the profiles of the cross section $y = \frac{1}{2}$ of the functions in the top row, zoomed in the interval $x \in [0.3, 0.7]$.

From Figures 6 to 9, we can observe that the non-oscillatory butterfly scheme behaves similarly to the linear kernel scheme in the vicinity of large gradients or edges while it is essentially the butterfly subdivision scheme in smooth regions. All examples show that, while the BSS produces undesired oscillations in the surroundings of large gradients in the data, the NOBSS is capable of avoiding this effect. Indeed, the absence of the Gibbs effect near large gradients or edges in the data is evident in all cases.

In the bottom of Figure 8, a comparison between the approximation errors of the BSS and NOBSS when approximating the function (45) is represented in logarithmic scale. It is remarkable that the red area around the data large gradients, which represents a large error, is narrower for NOBSS. However, since the approximation error does not capture the oscillatory behaviour of BSS in comparison with NOBSS, in the central row of Figure 8, the *signed error* (defined as the difference between the refined data and the exact function values, without computing the absolute value) is plotted in a log-scale style. In particular, the positive difference between the refined and the exact values are coloured from green (small error) to dark

Figure 7: Top row: The left figure is the function (44) where the red points and the black lines represent the initial data and the initial grid. The central and right figures are the refined data obtained with 5 iterations of the butterfly and the non-oscillatory butterfly schemes, respectively, when starting with the red data represented in the pictures. Bottom row: the profiles of the cross section $y = \frac{1}{2}$ of the functions in the top row.

red (large positive error) while, on the contrary, for negative differences a colour scale going from green (small error) to dark blue (large negative error) is used. In order to obtain a feasible representation of the signed error in a log-scale, any error in the interval $[-10^{-5}, 10^{-5}]$ is represented in green, while any error greater than 10^{-1} is represented with dark red (large positive error) and any error smaller than -10^{-1} is represented with dark blue (large negative error). Note that, to judge how large are these error values, the considered function (45) takes values in $]-\pi/2, \pi/2[$.

From the signed error plot we see very well the oscillations produced by BSS: In the left figure, corresponding to the BSS, the signed error presents several dark red/blue strips, while in the right one, corresponding to the NOBSS, there is only a single dark red strip and a single dark blue strip, located in the very next grid triangles to the large gradients of the data. This fact shows that NOBSS prevents the production of oscillations, in opposition to the classical BSS.

The last example in Figure 9 is to compare the NOBSS with the result obtained by applying the non-oscillatory interpolation technique working on quad-meshes, called “Nonlinear Piecewise Bicubic Hermite” and studied in [28]. For this purpose, we consider the function evaluations of (45) at the non-uniform triangular grid, as in Figure 8. From the picture we see that the NOBSS captures better the shape of the large gradients region. It is certainly because the NOBSS uses the three directions of the triangular grid to approximate that shape, resulting in a less “stepped” view in the figure.

Another advantage of using a triangular-mesh technique in comparison with a quad-mesh one, is that the last one is often not prepared to deal with non-uniform quad meshes. In contrast, a technique designed

Figure 8: Reconstruction of the function (45) using the butterfly (left) and the non-oscillatory butterfly (right) schemes. Top row: The red points and the black lines represent the initial data and the initial grid, while the surface represents the refined data obtained with 5 iterations of the subdivision schemes. Central and bottom rows: 2D coloured views of the difference between the reconstructed values and the exact function values (central row) and its absolute value (bottom row).

for non-uniform triangular meshes can manage data on any quad-mesh (just splitting each quadrilateral into two triangles).

170 5. Convergence

A crucial point in our study is to show the NOBSS convergence. The convergence proof we provide is based on the idea of writing the non-linear subdivision operator S_{NB} as ‘perturbation’ of a linear one, that

Figure 9: Reconstruction of the function (45) (left) using the NOBSS (center) and the “Nonlinear Piecewise Bicubic Hermite” proposed in [28] (right). The initial triangular and quadrilateral grids are represented as well.

is as

$$S_{\text{NB}} = K + \mathcal{F} \circ \Delta, \quad (46)$$

where K is the linear kernel subdivision operator associated with the three-direction Box-spline $B_{1,1,1}$, \mathcal{F} is a non-linear operator and Δ is the linear ‘difference’ operator defined in (7). To prove convergence of non-linear interpolatory subdivision operator of type (46) we can use [7, Theorem 3] presented below in a slightly different form adapted to our necessities.

Theorem 5.1 (Convergence and smoothness of a non-linear scheme). *Let \mathcal{S} be an interpolatory bivariate (non-linear) subdivision scheme based on the subdivision operator $S = K + \mathcal{F} \circ \Delta$, where $K : \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2) \rightarrow \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ is a linear subdivision operator whose associated scheme is convergent, $\Delta : \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2) \rightarrow \ell_\infty^6(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ is a linear operator and $\mathcal{F} : \ell_\infty^6(\mathbb{Z}^2) \rightarrow \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ a non-linear operator satisfying*

$$\exists M > 0 : \|\mathcal{F}(\delta)\|_\infty \leq M \|\delta\|_\infty, \quad \text{for all } \delta \in \ell_\infty^6(\mathbb{Z}^2), \quad (47)$$

$$\exists 0 < \mu < 1, k_0 \in \mathbb{Z}_+ : \|\Delta S^{k_0} \mathbf{f}\|_\infty \leq \mu \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_\infty, \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{f} \in \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2). \quad (48)$$

175 Then, \mathcal{S} is convergent.

To be able to use the previous result, we need some intermediate results whose proofs can be find in the Appendix. The first is that, for the interpolatory subdivision operator K associated with the three-direction Box-spline $B_{1,1,1}$ and for the difference operator Δ in (7), we can prove an interesting symbol ‘factorization’ property. We recall that for a subdivision operator $S : \ell(\mathbb{Z}^2) \rightarrow \ell(\mathbb{Z}^2)$, with mask $[s_j]_{j \in \mathbb{Z}^2}$ the associated
180 symbol is the Laurent polynomial $s(\xi) = \sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}^2} s_j \xi^j$.

Proposition 5.1. *Let K be the interpolatory subdivision operator associated with the three-direction Box-spline $B_{1,1,1}$ with refinement rule in (23) and let $\Delta : \ell(\mathbb{Z}) \rightarrow \ell^6(\mathbb{Z})$ be the difference operator defined in*

(7). Then, there exists a linear operator $K_\Delta : \ell^6(\mathbb{Z}^2) \longrightarrow \ell^6(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ such that

$$\Delta \circ K = K_\Delta \circ \Delta, \quad \text{with} \quad \|K_\Delta\|_\infty = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Remark 5.1. As a consequence of the previous proposition we have that

$$\|\Delta K \mathbf{f}\|_\infty = \|K_\Delta(\Delta \mathbf{f})\|_\infty \leq \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_\infty. \quad (49)$$

The second result is a technical lemma that will be useful in the convergence proof of the NOBSS whose proof can also be found in the Appendix.

Lemma 5.1. *Let be $\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ and $\mathbf{d} \in D$. If $\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{d} \notin 2\mathbb{Z}^2$, then there exists $\mathbf{j}' \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ and $\mathbf{d}', \mathbf{d}'' \in D$, $\mathbf{d}' \neq \mathbf{d}''$, such that*

$$|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}} K \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}}| = \frac{1}{2} |[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}', \mathbf{d}''} \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}'}|.$$

The last technicality we need is the definition of the operator $\chi : \ell^6(\mathbb{Z}^2) \longrightarrow \ell^6(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ acting on vectors of sequences, $\boldsymbol{\delta} = (\boldsymbol{\delta}^i)_{i=1}^6 \in \ell^6(\mathbb{Z}^2)$, as

$$[\chi(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}} = \begin{cases} 0 \in \mathbb{R}^6, & \mathbf{j} \in 2\mathbb{Z}^2, \\ (\boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(-1,-1)}^1, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(0,1)}^1, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(0,0)}^6, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(0,-1)}^6, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(-1,-1)}^4, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(0,0)}^4), & \mathbf{j} = 2\ell + (1, 0), \\ (\boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(0,-1)}^2, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(-1,0)}^2, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(-1,0)}^4, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(0,0)}^4, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(0,-1)}^5, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(0,0)}^5), & \mathbf{j} = 2\ell + (1, 1), \\ (\boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(1,0)}^3, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(-1,-1)}^3, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(-1,-1)}^5, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(0,0)}^5, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(0,0)}^6, \boldsymbol{\delta}_{\ell+(-1,0)}^6), & \mathbf{j} = 2\ell + (0, 1). \end{cases} \quad (50)$$

that satisfies $\|\chi\|_\infty = 1$. With some algebra we can see that when applied to the finite differences sequence $\Delta \mathbf{f}$, the operator χ provides the sequence

$$[\chi(\Delta \mathbf{f})]_{\mathbf{j}} = \begin{cases} 0 \in \mathbb{R}^6, & \mathbf{j} \in 2\mathbb{Z}^2, \\ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}}(\mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{j}}}) \in \mathbb{R}^6, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (51)$$

where $\Delta^{\mathcal{B}}$ is defined in (25). Based on χ , we define the operator $\mathcal{F} : \ell^6(\mathbb{Z}^2) \longrightarrow \ell(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ as

$$[\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{2\mathbf{j}} = 0, \quad [\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{2\mathbf{j}+\mathbf{d}} = \mathcal{G}_{\text{NB}}([\chi(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{2\mathbf{j}+\mathbf{d}}), \quad \mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2, \quad \mathbf{d} \in D. \quad (52)$$

With the operators (50) and (52), we are finally in a position to prove a convergence result.

Theorem 5.2. *The interpolatory non-linear butterfly subdivision scheme \mathcal{S}_{NB} defined in (41) is convergent.*

Proof. To prove the claim we heavily rely on Theorem 5.1 where, K is the ‘kernel’ scheme with refinement rule in (23), Δ is the difference operator in (7) and \mathcal{F} is in (52). First, we observe that (39) and (28) imply

$$|\mathcal{G}_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{w})| \leq \max \left\{ \frac{1}{16}|w_2| + \frac{1}{16}|w_1|, \frac{1}{16}|w_3| + \frac{1}{16}|w_5| + \frac{1}{16}|w_4| + \frac{1}{16}|w_6| \right\} \leq \frac{1}{4} \|w\|_\infty.$$

So that, since $\|\chi\|_\infty = 1$, it follows that \mathcal{F} in (52) fulfils (47) with $M = \frac{1}{4}$. It remains to show (48) that we will prove for $k_0 = 2$. We know that for any $\mathbf{f} \in \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ and $\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}' \in D$,

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f} = \nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} K \mathbf{f} + \nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} \mathcal{F}(\Delta \mathbf{f}).$$

Now, since $\|\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} K \mathbf{f}\|_\infty \leq \|\Delta K \mathbf{f}\|_\infty$ by definition of Δ , we can use Remark 5.1 and obtain

$$\|\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} K \mathbf{f}\|_\infty \leq \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_\infty. \quad (53)$$

Next, for $\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ and for any choice of $\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}' \in D$, we see that the difference

$$[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} \mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}} = [\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}} - [\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}+\mathbf{d}} - [\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}+\mathbf{d}'} + [\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}+\mathbf{d}+\mathbf{d}'}, \quad \boldsymbol{\delta} \in \ell_\infty^6(\mathbb{Z}^2), \quad (54)$$

uses at most 4 values of the sequence $\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})$, thus

$$|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} \mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}}| \leq 4 \|\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})\|_\infty. \quad (55)$$

By (40) and (51), we have that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\Delta \mathbf{f})\|_\infty \leq \frac{1}{8} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_\infty, \quad (56)$$

which, together with (55), implies that

$$\|\Delta \mathcal{F}(\Delta \mathbf{f})\|_\infty \leq \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_\infty, \quad \forall \mathbf{f} \in \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2). \quad (57)$$

Hence, by Remark 5.1 we conclude that

$$\|\Delta S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f}\|_\infty \leq \|\Delta K \mathbf{f}\|_\infty + \|\Delta \mathcal{F}(\Delta \mathbf{f})\|_\infty \leq \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_\infty + \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_\infty = \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_\infty. \quad (58)$$

Since from above we cannot conclude the validity of (48) for $k_0 = 1$, we proceed by computing $S_{\text{NB}}^2 \mathbf{f}$ that we write as

$$S_{\text{NB}}(S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f}) = K(S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f}) + \mathcal{F}(\Delta(S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f})), \quad (59)$$

and seek for a more accurate bound for $|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} \mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}}|$ than (55). For that purpose, we distinguish some cases for \mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}' and \mathbf{j} . If $\mathbf{d} \neq \mathbf{d}'$, it can be easily checked that at least one of the four values is zero in (54), since its subscript belongs to $2\mathbb{Z}^2$ and by definition $[\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}} = 0$, for any $\boldsymbol{\ell} \in \mathbb{Z}^2$. As a consequence,

$$|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} \mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}}| \leq 3 \|\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})\|_\infty, \quad \forall \mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2, \quad \forall \mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}' \in D, \mathbf{d} \neq \mathbf{d}'. \quad (60)$$

If $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{d}'$, (54) becomes

$$[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}} \mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}} = [\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}} - 2[\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}+\mathbf{d}} + [\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}+2\mathbf{d}},$$

and if $\mathbf{j} \in 2\mathbb{Z}^2$ (and then $\mathbf{j} + 2\mathbf{d} \in 2\mathbb{Z}^2$) or $\mathbf{j} + \mathbf{d} \in 2\mathbb{Z}^2$, some elements are zeros and we get

$$|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}} \mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})]_{\mathbf{j}}| \leq 2 \|\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta})\|_\infty. \quad (61)$$

Collecting the results of the three situations (55), (60) and (61), and applying (56), we obtain

$$|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} \mathcal{F}(\Delta \mathbf{f})]_{\mathbf{j}}| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty}, & \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{d}', \text{ and } \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{d} \notin 2\mathbb{Z}^2, \\ \frac{1}{4} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty}, & \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{d}', \text{ and } (\mathbf{j} \in 2\mathbb{Z}^2 \text{ or } \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{d} \in 2\mathbb{Z}^2), \\ \frac{3}{8} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty}, & \mathbf{d} \neq \mathbf{d}', \end{cases}$$

or simply

$$|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} \mathcal{F}(\Delta \mathbf{f})]_{\mathbf{j}}| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty}, & \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{d}', \text{ and } \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{d} \notin 2\mathbb{Z}^2, \\ \frac{3}{8} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (62)$$

Now, we consider the situation when $\mathbf{d} \neq \mathbf{d}'$ either $\mathbf{j} \in 2\mathbb{Z}^2$ or $\mathbf{j} + \mathbf{d} \in 2\mathbb{Z}^2$ and show that it results $|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} S_{\text{NB}}^2 \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}}| \leq \frac{7}{8} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty}$. Indeed, from (59) we have for $\mathbf{f} \in \ell_{\infty}(\mathbb{Z}^2)$

$$|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} S_{\text{NB}}^2 \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}}| \leq |[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} K S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}}| + |[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} \mathcal{F}(\Delta S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f})]_{\mathbf{j}}| \leq \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty} + \frac{3}{8} \|\Delta S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty} = \frac{7}{8} \|\Delta S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty} \quad (63)$$

that, combined with (58), provides

$$|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}'} S_{\text{NB}}^2 \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}}| \leq \frac{7}{8} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty}.$$

When $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{d}'$ and $\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{d} \notin 2\mathbb{Z}^2$, according to Lemma 5.1, we know that there exists $\mathbf{j}' \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{d}}, \tilde{\mathbf{d}}' \in D$, $\tilde{\mathbf{d}} \neq \tilde{\mathbf{d}}'$, such that

$$|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}} K \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}}| = \frac{1}{2} |[\nabla_{\tilde{\mathbf{d}}, \tilde{\mathbf{d}}'} \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}'}|.$$

Then, from (59) and (62) we have

$$\begin{aligned} |[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}} S_{\text{NB}}^2 \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}}| &\leq |[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}} K S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}}| + |[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}} \mathcal{F}(\Delta S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f})]_{\mathbf{j}}| \leq \frac{1}{2} |[\nabla_{\tilde{\mathbf{d}}, \tilde{\mathbf{d}}'} S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}'}| + \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} |[\nabla_{\tilde{\mathbf{d}}, \tilde{\mathbf{d}}'} K \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}'}| + \frac{1}{2} |[\nabla_{\tilde{\mathbf{d}}, \tilde{\mathbf{d}}'} \mathcal{F}(\Delta \mathbf{f})]_{\mathbf{j}'}| + \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta S_{\text{NB}} \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{3}{8} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty} + \frac{1}{2} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty} = \frac{15}{16} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty}. \end{aligned}$$

From above we conclude that

$$\|\Delta S_{\text{NB}}^2 \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty} \leq \frac{15}{16} \|\Delta \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty}, \quad \forall \mathbf{f} \in \ell_{\infty}(\mathbb{Z}^2),$$

185 which is the level-2 contractivity of the subdivision operator S_{NB} . □

Remark 5.2. Observe that, in the previous proof, only properties (10) and (12) of A were used. Therefore, it is straightforward to see that the same convergence result for the subdivision scheme (34) can be obtained for any choice of averages $\mathcal{A}, \hat{\mathcal{A}}, \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ such that \mathcal{A} fulfils (10) and $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and $\hat{\mathcal{A}}$ fulfil (12) for $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$.

6. Approximation order

190 This section is devoted to the study of the approximation order of the NOBSS under the assumption that the data function is smooth. Thanks to the locality of the subdivision scheme, the results are valid for piecewise smooth functions, in those smooth regions far enough from discontinuities.

We will study the approximation order through the *step-wise approximation order* defined below and connected with the approximation order via the notion of stability that we will discuss in Section 7.

Definition 6.1. A subdivision scheme \mathcal{S} based on the subdivision operator S has *step-wise approximation order* r if there exists $h_0 > 0$ such that for any $F \in \mathcal{C}^r(\mathbb{R}^2)$ with bounded derivatives up to order r ,

$$\left\| S [F(h\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2} - [F(h\mathbf{j}/2)]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2} \right\|_{\infty} = \mathcal{O}(h^r; F), \quad 0 < h < h_0.$$

195 *Remark 6.1.* Usually, the dependence of the last \mathcal{O} -expression depends on the uniform bound of some derivatives of F . The present study is not an exception and we will see in the former results which derivatives are required to be bound for the proposed scheme.

We will see that the NOBSS has step-wise approximation order 4 (as much as the butterfly scheme) under certain hypothesis on the partial derivatives of the function to be approximated, a typical behaviour of non-
200 linear schemes that uses non-linear averages in this way (see [14], for example). To prove the approximation order result, we need the following technical Lemma whose proof is in the Appendix.

Lemma 6.1. *Let $F \in \mathcal{C}^4(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be with partial derivatives up to fourth order bounded in modulus by a constant $\sigma' > 0$. Then, there exist $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3 > 0$, which depend on σ' , such that for any $\mathbf{d} \in D$, $h > 0$ and $\boldsymbol{\ell} \in \mathbb{Z}^2$, taking $\mathbf{p} = h(\boldsymbol{\ell} + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{d})$, $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+\mathbf{d}}}$ and $\mathbf{f} = [F(h\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2}$,*

$$|\Psi_K(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p})| \leq \theta_1 h^2, \quad |\Psi_B(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p})| \leq \theta_2 h^4, \quad |\Psi_C(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p})| \leq \theta_3 h^3, \quad C \in \{N, S, W, E\}. \quad (64)$$

Moreover, if $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} > \sigma$, $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} > \sigma$, and $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y} > \sigma$, for some $\sigma > 0$, then

$$(\mathcal{G}_C \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}) = \mathcal{O}(h^2; \sigma, \sigma'), \quad C \in \{N, S, W, E\}, \quad (65)$$

Also, there exists $h_0 > 0$ depending on σ, σ' such that

$$(\mathcal{G}_C \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}) < 0, \quad \text{for } 0 < h < h_0. \quad (66)$$

In addition, there exists $M > 0$ and $h_1 > 0$, which depend on σ, σ' , such that

$$\left| 1 - \frac{(\mathcal{G}_S \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})}{(\mathcal{G}_N \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})} \right| \leq Mh, \quad \left| 1 - \frac{(\mathcal{G}_E \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})}{(\mathcal{G}_W \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})} \right| \leq Mh, \quad \text{for } h < h_1. \quad (67)$$

With the previous Lemma we arrive at the approximation order result.

Theorem 6.1. *Let F be a function with partial derivatives up to order 4 bounded in modulus by a constant $\sigma' > 0$ and such that $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} > \sigma$, $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} > \sigma$, and $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y} > \sigma$, for some $\sigma > 0$. Then, the non-oscillatory butterfly subdivision operator and the butterfly subdivision operator coincide when applied to data $\mathbf{f} = [F(h\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2}$, for h small enough.*

Proof. Let $\mathbf{d} \in D$, $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}^2$, $h > 0$, $\mathbf{p} = F(h(\ell + \mathbf{d}/2))$, $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_{2\ell+\mathbf{d}}}$ and $\mathbf{f} = [F(h\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2}$. We recall the refinement rule of the NOBSS:

$$\Psi_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{z}) = \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}) + \text{H}_1 \left(A((\mathcal{G}_{\text{N}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}), (\mathcal{G}_{\text{S}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})), A((\mathcal{G}_{\text{W}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}), (\mathcal{G}_{\text{E}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})) \right).$$

Denoting with $\mathcal{L}(x, y)$ the linear average of x and y , $\mathcal{L}(x, y) = \frac{1}{2}x + \frac{1}{2}y$, due to (22) the refinement rule of the BSS can be similarly written as

$$\Psi_{\text{B}}(\mathbf{z}) = \Psi_{\text{K}}(\mathbf{z}) + \text{H}_1 \left(\mathcal{L}((\mathcal{G}_{\text{N}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}), (\mathcal{G}_{\text{S}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})), \mathcal{L}((\mathcal{G}_{\text{W}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}), (\mathcal{G}_{\text{E}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})) \right).$$

Using Lemma 6.1 we obtain that $(\mathcal{G}_C \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})$, $C \in \{\text{N}, \text{S}, \text{W}, \text{E}\}$, are negative for h small enough. Still from Lemma 6.1 we see that, as functions of h , there exist $M > 0$ and $h_0 > 0$ such that these quantities fulfil

$$\left| 1 - \frac{(\mathcal{G}_{\text{S}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})}{(\mathcal{G}_{\text{N}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})} \right| \leq Mh, \quad \left| 1 - \frac{(\mathcal{G}_{\text{E}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})}{(\mathcal{G}_{\text{W}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})} \right| \leq Mh, \quad \text{for } h < h_0,$$

where M and h_0 depends on σ and σ' . By Lemma 9.1 in Appendix for $c = \frac{4}{3}$, $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$, we know that there exists $\tau_1 > 0$, depending on M, h_0 , such that for $h < \tau_1$

$$\begin{aligned} A((\mathcal{G}_{\text{N}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}), (\mathcal{G}_{\text{S}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})) &= \mathcal{L}((\mathcal{G}_{\text{N}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}), (\mathcal{G}_{\text{S}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})), \\ A((\mathcal{G}_{\text{W}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}), (\mathcal{G}_{\text{E}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})) &= \mathcal{L}((\mathcal{G}_{\text{W}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}), (\mathcal{G}_{\text{E}} \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\Psi_{\text{NB}}(\mathbf{z}) = \Psi_{\text{B}}(\mathbf{z})$ for all $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_{2\ell+\mathbf{d}}}$, $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}^2$, $\mathbf{d} \in D$, $\mathbf{f} = [F(h\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2}$, and $h < \tau_1$ which concludes the proof. \square

From the previous Theorem the step-wise approximation order follows as a Corollary.

Corollary 6.1. *Under the hypothesis of Theorem 6.1, the NOBSS has step-wise approximation order 4.*

Remark 6.2. We note that, since the proposed scheme is 1-homogenous (due to (9) and (34)) the assumption that $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}$, $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2}$, $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y}$ are strictly positive can be replaced with strictly negative partial derivatives.

7. Numerical investigation of the NOBSS

This section is to present a numerical discussion of the stability/instability of the NOBSS scheme together with numerical confirmations of its approximation order linked to the theoretical results in Section 6. The

numerical investigation of the stability/instability is to explain the choice of the non-linear averages H_1 and $A_{\frac{4}{3}, \frac{1}{2}}$ that we use in the definition of the NOBSS. In fact, our numerical experiments show that, selecting $A_{c, \frac{1}{2}}$ in (37) as A , the corresponding NOBSS show evidence of instability for c larger than a certain threshold.

Keeping in mind that the scheme is stable if there exists $M > 0$ such that

$$\|S_{\text{NB}}^\infty \mathbf{f}^{(0)} - S_{\text{NB}}^\infty \mathbf{g}^{(0)}\|_\infty \leq M \|\mathbf{f}^{(0)} - \mathbf{g}^{(0)}\|_\infty, \quad \mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \mathbf{g}^{(0)} \in \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2), \quad \mathbf{f}^{(0)} \neq \mathbf{g}^{(0)}, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0, \quad (68)$$

and that S_{NB} is 1-homogenous (due to (9) and (34)), we study the operators

$$L_k(\mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \mathbf{g}^{(0)}) := \frac{\|S_{\text{NB}}^k \mathbf{f}^{(0)} - S_{\text{NB}}^k \mathbf{g}^{(0)}\|_\infty}{\|\mathbf{f}^{(0)} - \mathbf{g}^{(0)}\|_\infty}, \quad \mathbf{f}^{(0)} \neq \mathbf{g}^{(0)}, \quad \|\mathbf{f}^{(0)}\|_\infty = 1, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0, \quad (69)$$

and compute the quantities

$$M_k = \sup\{L_k(\mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \mathbf{g}^{(0)}) \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{f}^{(0)} \neq \mathbf{g}^{(0)}, \quad \|\mathbf{f}^{(0)}\|_\infty = 1\}, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0.$$

Since the subdivision operator S_{NB} is Lipschitz, each operator L_k is bounded from above by $M_k < \infty$ and the scheme is stable if the sequence $\{M_k\}_{k=0}^\infty$ converges to a constant, which is exactly M in (68).

To numerically compute M_k , due to the locality of the NOBSS and to the size of its stencil, aiming at simulating the first derivatives we restrict the computation of (69) to finite sequences $\mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \mathbf{g}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$ with $\mathbf{g}^{(0)} := \mathbf{f}^{(0)} + h\boldsymbol{\theta}$, $h \ll 1$ (we take $h = 10^{-8}$) and $\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$, $\sup_j |[\boldsymbol{\theta}]_j| = 1$, because the supreme of L_k is reached when $h \rightarrow 0$. Using a global optimizer of the Matlab-Toolbox, we compute

$$\hat{M}_k = \max\{L_k(\mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \mathbf{f}^{(0)} + h\boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}, \sup_j |[\mathbf{f}^{(0)}]_j| = \sup_j |[\boldsymbol{\theta}]_j| = 1, h = 10^{-8}\}, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0.$$

The results obtained for $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$ are reported in Table 1, showing that the larger is c , the larger is \hat{M}_k . The table also shows that for $c = 1$ and $c = 1.2$ the value \hat{M}_k exhibits a moderate growth, which indicates stability, while an unstable behaviour appears for $c = 2$.

	\hat{M}_1	\hat{M}_2	\hat{M}_3	\hat{M}_4
$c = 1$	1.500	1.7187	1.7852	1.7852
$c = 1.2$	1.7200	2.2240	2.2240	2.2794
$c = 2$	4.000	10.5000	21.2500	38.6250

Table 1: Numerical computation of the stability indicator \hat{M}_k for the NOBSS obtained from the non-linear averages $\mathcal{A} = \tilde{\mathcal{A}} = \hat{\mathcal{A}} = A_{c, \lambda}$, $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$.

For a more accurate analysis of the stability, we recall a result given by [15, Théorème II.12] often used in the stability analysis of non-linear schemes. We present it adapted to our notation as done in Theorem 5.1.

Theorem 7.1 (Stability of a non-linear scheme). *Let \mathcal{S} be a convergent interpolatory bivariate (non-linear) subdivision scheme based on the subdivision operator $S = K + \mathcal{F} \circ \Delta$, where $K : \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2) \rightarrow \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ is a linear subdivision operator, whose associated scheme is convergent, $\Delta : \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2) \rightarrow \ell_\infty^6(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ is a linear operator and $\mathcal{F} : \ell_\infty^6(\mathbb{Z}^2) \rightarrow \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ a non-linear operator satisfying*

$$\exists M > 0 : \|\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta}) - \mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\delta}')\|_\infty \leq M\|\boldsymbol{\delta} - \boldsymbol{\delta}'\|_\infty, \quad \text{for all } \boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\delta}' \in \ell_\infty^6(\mathbb{Z}^2), \quad (70)$$

$$\exists 0 < \mu < 1, k_0 \in \mathbb{Z}_+ : \|\Delta(S^{k_0} \mathbf{f} - S^{k_0} \mathbf{g})\|_\infty \leq \mu \|\Delta(\mathbf{f} - \mathbf{g})\|_\infty, \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{g} \in \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2). \quad (71)$$

Then, \mathcal{S} is stable.

In light of Theorem 7.1, we introduce a second indicator of stability:

$$L_k^\Delta(\mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \mathbf{g}^{(0)}) := \frac{\|\Delta(S_{\text{NB}}^k \mathbf{f}^{(0)} - S_{\text{NB}}^k \mathbf{g}^{(0)})\|_\infty}{\|\Delta(\mathbf{f}^{(0)} - \mathbf{g}^{(0)})\|_\infty}, \quad \Delta \mathbf{f}^{(0)} \neq \Delta \mathbf{g}^{(0)}, \quad \|\mathbf{f}^{(0)}\|_\infty = 1, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0. \quad (72)$$

If there exist $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\mu > 0$ such that $L_{k_0}^\Delta(\mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \mathbf{g}^{(0)}) < \mu < 1$ for all $\mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \mathbf{g}^{(0)} \in \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z}^2)$, $\Delta \mathbf{f}^{(0)} \neq \Delta \mathbf{g}^{(0)}$, $\|\mathbf{f}^{(0)}\|_\infty = 1$, then the scheme is stable. On the contrary, if we find a couple $(\mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \mathbf{g}^{(0)})$ such that $L_k^\Delta(\mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \mathbf{g}^{(0)}) \geq 1$ for some k , then, k needs to be increased in order to use Theorem 7.1.

For the NOBSS and for $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$ we compute an estimation of the L_k^Δ supremum, that we call \hat{M}_k^Δ , with the same methodology as for \hat{M}_k . The results are shown in Table 2. The scheme shows stability for

	\hat{M}_1^Δ	\hat{M}_2^Δ	\hat{M}_3^Δ	\hat{M}_4^Δ
$c = 1$	1	0.7764	0.5030	0.2864
$c = 1.1$	1.1050	0.9300	0.5837	0.4168
$c = 1.2$	1.2300	1.0838	0.7748	0.5206
$c = 1.3$	1.4486	1.4114	1.1770	0.9341
$c = 2$	3.4371	5.8453	10.7704	11.9426

Table 2: Numerical computation of the stability indicator \hat{M}_k^Δ for the NOBSS obtained from the non-linear averages $\mathcal{A} = \tilde{\mathcal{A}} = \hat{\mathcal{A}} = A_{c,\lambda}$, $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$.

$c \in \{1, 1.1, 1.2, 1.3\}$, and $k \geq 2$. For $c = 1$ and $c = 1.1$, $k = 2$ iterations seem to be enough; for $c = 1.2$, to get stability we need to consider $k = 3$; and for $c = 1.3$, $k = 4$. For $c = 2$, the larger is k , the larger is \hat{M}_k^Δ . Note that, even though $\hat{M}_k^\Delta < 1$ cannot be taken as a rigorous proof of stability of the scheme, in case $\hat{M}_k^\Delta \geq 1$ we can conclude that the use of Theorem 7.1 requires $k \geq 2$, that requires very hard computations.

From the previous discussion we draw the following conclusions: On the one hand, it is convenient to consider the non-linear averages $A_{c,\lambda}$ with c as close as possible to 1 to obtain a small \hat{M}_k , and, with

this respect, thanks to (22) the choice $\mathcal{A} = A_{1,\lambda} = H_1$ is the best possible. On the other hand, since for
240 $\tilde{\mathcal{A}} = \hat{\mathcal{A}} = A_{c,\frac{1}{2}}$, the larger is c the closer is the NOBSS to the BSS in smooth regions (with maximum
approximation order for any $c > 1$), c should be taken as large as possible but inside the stability range.
In conclusion, the selection $\mathcal{A} = H_1$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{A}} = \hat{\mathcal{A}} = A_{\frac{4}{3},\frac{1}{2}}$ is the one that appears to guarantee accuracy and
stability, as shown in Table 3.

\hat{M}_1^Δ	\hat{M}_2^Δ	\hat{M}_3^Δ	\hat{M}_4^Δ
1.1667	0.9822	0.6805	0.4718

Table 3: Numerical computation of the stability indicator \hat{M}_k^Δ for the NOBSS obtained from the non-linear averages $\mathcal{A} = H_1$,
 $\tilde{\mathcal{A}} = \hat{\mathcal{A}} = A_{\frac{4}{3},\frac{1}{2}}$.

We conclude this section with a numerical discussion of the approximation order of the NOBSS that
245 confirms the theoretical estimates given in Section 6. It also shows that the set of functions that satisfy the
assumption of Theorem 6.1 is non-empty.

We consider the Gaussian function

$$F(x, y) = \exp(-(x^2 + y^2)/8), \quad (x, y) \in [-2, 2] \times [-2, 2], \quad (73)$$

whose partial derivatives $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}$, $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2}$, and $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y}$, are strictly negative in the domain $[-1, 1] \times [-1, 1]$,
while they change sign in $[-2, 2] \times [-2, 2]$ as shown in Figure 10 where we plot the zeros of these partial
derivatives.

Figure 10: From left to right, the two (blue) curves are the zeros of the functions $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}$, $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2}$ and $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y}$ for the
Gaussian function (73). Between the curves, the partial derivatives are negative, while outside they are positive.

According to the Corollary 6.1, the step-wise approximation order is 4 and, together with the stability
discussed above, it would imply approximation order 4. To numerically check it, we consider a uniform grid
with spacing $h = 0.2$ and compute the level-5 approximation error inside a fixed subdomain of F ,

$$e_R^h = \sup\{|(S_{NB}^5 f)_j - F(2^{-5} h \mathbf{j})| : 2^{-5} h \mathbf{j} \in R\}, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0.$$

250 Table 4 shows the values $\rho_R^h := \log_2 \frac{e_R^h}{e_R^{h/2}}$, for $h = 0.2, 0.1, 0.05, 0.025$, for $R = [-1, 1] \times [-1, 1]$ and $R =$
 $[-1.6, 1.6] \times [-1.6, 1.6]$. The table shows that only when e_R^h is computed with data in the region where

the partial derivatives are negative, that is $R = [-1, 1] \times [-1, 1]$, the decay rate $e_R^h = \mathcal{O}(h^4)$ is numerically confirmed. This is not the case when e_R^h is computed involving data in regions where the sign of the partial derivatives changes, as $R = [-1.6, 1.6] \times [-1.6, 1.6]$.

ρ_R^h	h=0.2	h=0.1	h=0.05	h=0.025
$R = [-1, 1] \times [-1, 1]$	3.9901	3.9975	3.9994	3.9998
$R = [-1.6, 1.6] \times [-1.6, 1.6]$	3.0018	3.2696	2.7039	2.9721

Table 4: Approximation order of the non-linear scheme depending on the derivatives of the function at the region R .

255 8. Conclusion and future work

This paper proposes and analyses a non-oscillatory interpolatory scheme for data on three-directional regular grids. Non-linear analogue of the well known butterfly subdivision scheme, our approach is capable of eliminating the Gibbs-like oscillatory behaviour when applied to discrete data with large gradients, a common situation in the numerical simulation of conservation laws, for example.

260 After an accurate description of the new proposal, convergence, reproduction and accuracy of the scheme are investigated. Several numerical examples are shown proving that, while the butterfly subdivision scheme produces undesired oscillations in the surroundings of large gradients in the data, its non-oscillatory version is capable of avoiding this effect.

This work is a first attempt in the design of non-oscillatory subdivision schemes for triangular meshes. 265 Future work will investigate how different averages influence the reduction of Gibbs effects (see [29, 30]) but also how to improve the approximation order in the vicinity of the discontinuity, for example by moving from polynomial interpolation to exponential-polynomial interpolation (see [31, 32]). Our intention is to theoretically study the behaviour of this non-oscillatory interpolatory scheme when data is attached to non-regular triangular grids, and maybe propose some improvement. Last, but not least, more points to the 270 stencil can be added to the scheme, perhaps leading to a more accurate preservation of the large-gradients region shapes.

Acknowledgements

The first author is member of INdAM-GNCS, Italy, partially supporting this work. The second author has been supported by grant PID2020-117211GB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by 275 the short-stay scholarship BEST/2021/159 funded by Generalitat Valenciana.

The authors also thanks professor Francesc Arandiga (Universitat de València) for providing the MATLAB implementation of the “Nonlinear Piecewise Bicubic Hermite” interpolation method.

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345 9. Appendix

This Appendix is to collect the proofs of several technical results presented and used in the previous sections. For the reader convenience, we also repeat the statements of the results.

Proposition 2.1. *The two-parameter average $A_{c,\lambda}$ defined in (17) for $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ and $c > 1$ is Lipschitz continuous and fulfils properties **P1** and **P2** for any $p \geq 1$ and for any $\tilde{c} \geq c$.*

350 *Proof.* For $x \cdot y \leq 0$, $A(x, y) = 0$, and for $x \cdot y > 0$, $A(x, y) = \min \{|\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y|, c \cdot |x|, c \cdot |y|\}$. In both cases, A is the composition of Lipschitz continuous functions. From the continuity of A , we derive Lipschitz condition as well.

To verify conditions from (9) to (12) is simple by direct inspection. A bit more complicated is to show (13), for any $p > 0$, which we show next. In particular, we show that for $x \in \mathbb{R}$, $x \neq 0$, there exist $h_0 > 0$, depending on c, λ , such that

$$A_{c,\lambda}(x, x + h) = \lambda x + (1 - \lambda)(x + h), \quad |h| < h_0. \quad (74)$$

We assume without loss of generality that $h_0 < |x|$, so x and $x + h$ have the same sign for any $h \in \mathbb{R}$, $|h| < h_0$. We are going to prove that for each $x \neq 0$, there exists $h_0 > 0$ such that

$$|\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)(x + h)| \leq c \min\{|x|, |x + h|\}, \quad |h| < h_0. \quad (75)$$

In that case, by definition, $A_{c,\lambda}(x, x + h) = \lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y$, and the claim follows. To show (75) we first observe that

$$|\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)(x + h)| = |x + (1 - \lambda)h| \leq |x| + (1 - \lambda)|h|,$$

and that

$$c \min\{|x|, |x + h|\} \geq c \min\{|x|, |x| - |h|\} = c(|x| - |h|).$$

Therefore, since for $|h| \leq |x| \frac{c-1}{1-\lambda+c}$ we have that $|x| + (1 - \lambda)|h| \leq c(|x| - |h|)$, then (75) holds true for $h_0 := \frac{c-1}{1-\lambda+c}|x| > 0$, which fulfils $h_0 < |x|$. \square

Lemma 9.1. *Let $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ be such that there exist $M > 0$ and $\tau_0 > 0$,*

$$\left| \frac{g(\tau)}{f(\tau)} - 1 \right| \leq M\tau, \quad |\tau| < \tau_0. \quad (76)$$

Then, for the average $A_{c,\lambda}$, there exists $\tau_1 > 0$, depending on M, τ_0, c, λ , such that

$$A_{c,\lambda}(f(\tau), g(\tau)) = \lambda f(\tau) + (1 - \lambda)g(\tau), \quad \text{for } |\tau| < \tau_1.$$

Proof. By the 1-homogeneous property in (9), since $f(\tau) \neq 0$ we have that

$$A_{c,\lambda}(f(\tau), g(\tau)) = f(\tau) A_{c,\lambda} \left(1, \frac{g(\tau)}{f(\tau)} \right). \quad (77)$$

By (74) in Proposition 2.1 for $x = 1$, there exists $h_0 > 0$ depending on c, λ such that

$$A_{c,\lambda}(1, 1 + h) = \lambda + (1 - \lambda)(1 + h), \quad |h| < h_0. \quad (78)$$

Hence, for $|\tau| < \tau_1 := \min\{\tau_0, h_0/M\}$,

$$\left| \frac{g(\tau)}{f(\tau)} - 1 \right| \leq M\tau < Mh_0/M = h_0,$$

we can apply (78) with $h = \frac{g(\tau)}{f(\tau)} - 1$ and obtain

$$A_{c,\lambda} \left(1, \frac{g(\tau)}{f(\tau)} \right) = \lambda + (1 - \lambda) \frac{g(\tau)}{f(\tau)}, \quad |\tau| < \tau_1.$$

Then, by (77),

$$A_{c,\lambda}(f(\tau), g(\tau)) = f(\tau) \left(\lambda + (1 - \lambda) \frac{g(\tau)}{f(\tau)} \right) = \lambda f(\tau) + (1 - \lambda)g(\tau), \quad \text{for } |\tau| < \tau_1,$$

355 which concludes the proof. \square

Proposition 5.1. *Let K be the interpolatory subdivision operator associated with the three-direction B-spline $B_{1,1,1}$ with refinement rule in (23) and let $\Delta : \ell(\mathbb{Z}) \rightarrow \ell^6(\mathbb{Z})$ be the difference operator defined in (7). Then, there exists a linear operator $K_\Delta : \ell^6(\mathbb{Z}^2) \rightarrow \ell^6(\mathbb{Z}^2)$ such that*

$$\Delta \circ K = K_\Delta \circ \Delta, \quad \text{with} \quad \|K_\Delta\|_\infty = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Proof. The symbol of the linear subdivision operator K is (see [27] for details)

$$K(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \frac{1}{2\xi_1\xi_2}(1 + \xi_1)(1 + \xi_2)(1 + \xi_1\xi_2). \quad (79)$$

Therefore,

$$\|K\|_\infty := \max \left\{ \sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}^2} |k_{\mathbf{e}+2\mathbf{j}}| : \mathbf{e} \in \{(0,0), (1,0), (1,1), (0,1)\} \right\} = \max\{1, 1, 1, 1\} = 1,$$

hence, $\|K\mathbf{f}\|_\infty \leq \|K\|_\infty \|\mathbf{f}\|_\infty = \|\mathbf{f}\|_\infty$ for all $\mathbf{f} \in \ell_\infty(\mathbb{Z})$. The symbol of the finite difference operator in (7) is the vector Laurent polynomial

$$\Delta(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = ((1 - \xi_1)^2, (1 - \xi_1\xi_2)^2, (1 - \xi_2)^2, (1 - \xi_1)(1 - \xi_1\xi_2), (1 - \xi_2)(1 - \xi_1\xi_2), (1 - \xi_1)(1 - \xi_2))^T.$$

It is not difficult to see via matrix-vector multiplication, that the matrix symbol $K_\Delta(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ of dimension 6×6

$$K_\Delta(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \frac{1}{2\xi_1\xi_2} \begin{pmatrix} \xi_2 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & -\xi_1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \xi_2 & \xi_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \xi_1 & 0 & 1 & -\xi_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \xi_2 + 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \xi_1 + 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 + \xi_1\xi_2 \end{pmatrix},$$

satisfies $\Delta(\boldsymbol{\xi})K(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = K_\Delta(\boldsymbol{\xi})\Delta(\boldsymbol{\xi}^2)$. To compute

$$\|K_\Delta\|_\infty := \max \left\{ \sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}^2} \|k_{\mathbf{e}+2\mathbf{j}}^\Delta\|_\infty : \mathbf{e} \in \{(0,0), (1,0), (1,1), (0,1)\} \right\},$$

we write $K_\Delta(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_1 \xi_2 K_\Delta(\boldsymbol{\xi}) &= \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + \frac{\xi_2}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\ &+ \frac{\xi_1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \frac{\xi_1 \xi_2}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned}$$

and since the infinity norm of the four matrices defining $K_\Delta(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ are $\frac{1}{2}$, we have that $\|K_\Delta\|_\infty = \frac{1}{2}$. \square

Lemma 5.1. *Let be $\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ and $\mathbf{d} \in D$. If $\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{d} \notin 2\mathbb{Z}^2$, then there exists $\mathbf{j}' \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ and $\mathbf{d}', \mathbf{d}'' \in D$, $\mathbf{d}' \neq \mathbf{d}''$, such that*

$$|[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}} K \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}}| = \frac{1}{2} |[\nabla_{\mathbf{d}', \mathbf{d}''} \mathbf{f}]_{\mathbf{j}'}|.$$

Proof. We only need to take into account two facts, from which the claim follows. First,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j} + (1, 0) \notin 2\mathbb{Z}^2 &\longrightarrow \exists \boldsymbol{\ell} \in \mathbb{Z}^2 : \mathbf{j} = 2\boldsymbol{\ell} + (0, 1) \text{ or } 2\boldsymbol{\ell} + (1, 1), \\ \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j} + (1, 1) \notin 2\mathbb{Z}^2 &\longrightarrow \exists \boldsymbol{\ell} \in \mathbb{Z}^2 : \mathbf{j} = 2\boldsymbol{\ell} + (1, 0) \text{ or } 2\boldsymbol{\ell} + (0, 1), \\ \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j} + (0, 1) \notin 2\mathbb{Z}^2 &\longrightarrow \exists \boldsymbol{\ell} \in \mathbb{Z}^2 : \mathbf{j} = 2\boldsymbol{\ell} + (1, 0) \text{ or } 2\boldsymbol{\ell} + (1, 1). \end{aligned}$$

Second,

$$\begin{aligned} [\nabla_{(1,0),(1,0)} K \mathbf{f}]_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+(0,1)} &= -\frac{1}{2} [\nabla_{(1,0),(0,1)} \mathbf{f}]_{\boldsymbol{\ell}}, & [\nabla_{(1,0),(1,0)} K \mathbf{f}]_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+(1,1)} &= \frac{1}{2} [\nabla_{(1,0),(1,1)} \mathbf{f}]_{\boldsymbol{\ell}}, \\ [\nabla_{(1,1),(1,1)} K \mathbf{f}]_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+(1,0)} &= \frac{1}{2} [\nabla_{(1,0),(1,1)} \mathbf{f}]_{\boldsymbol{\ell}}, & [\nabla_{(1,1),(1,1)} K \mathbf{f}]_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+(0,1)} &= \frac{1}{2} [\nabla_{(0,1),(1,1)} \mathbf{f}]_{\boldsymbol{\ell}}, \\ [\nabla_{(0,1),(0,1)} K \mathbf{f}]_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+(1,0)} &= -\frac{1}{2} [\nabla_{(1,0),(0,1)} \mathbf{f}]_{\boldsymbol{\ell}}, & [\nabla_{(0,1),(0,1)} K \mathbf{f}]_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+(1,1)} &= \frac{1}{2} [\nabla_{(0,1),(1,1)} \mathbf{f}]_{\boldsymbol{\ell}}. \end{aligned}$$

\square

Lemma 6.1. *Let $F \in \mathcal{C}^4(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be with partial derivatives up to forth order bounded in modulus by a constant $\sigma' > 0$. Then, there exist $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3 > 0$, which depend on σ' , such that for any $\mathbf{d} \in D$, $h > 0$ and $\boldsymbol{\ell} \in \mathbb{Z}^2$, taking $\mathbf{p} = h(\boldsymbol{\ell} + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{d})$, $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+\mathbf{d}}}$ and $\mathbf{f} = [F(h\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2}$,*

$$|\Psi_K(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p})| \leq \theta_1 h^2, \quad |\Psi_B(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p})| \leq \theta_2 h^4, \quad |\Psi_C(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p})| \leq \theta_3 h^3, \quad C \in \{N, S, W, E\}. \quad (64)$$

Moreover, if $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} > \sigma$, $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} > \sigma$, and $\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y} > \sigma$, for some $\sigma > 0$, then

$$(\mathcal{G}_C \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}) = \mathcal{O}(h^2; \sigma, \sigma'), \quad C \in \{N, S, W, E\}, \quad (65)$$

Also, there exists $h_0 > 0$ depending on σ, σ' such that

$$(\mathcal{G}_C \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}) < 0, \quad \text{for } 0 < h < h_0. \quad (66)$$

In addition, there exists $M > 0$ and $h_1 > 0$, which depend on σ, σ' , such that

$$\left| 1 - \frac{(\mathcal{G}_S \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})}{(\mathcal{G}_N \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})} \right| \leq Mh, \quad \left| 1 - \frac{(\mathcal{G}_E \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})}{(\mathcal{G}_W \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})} \right| \leq Mh, \quad \text{for } h < h_1. \quad (67)$$

Proof. We show the details for $\mathbf{d} = (1, 0)$. The same analysis can be done for the other $\mathbf{d} \in D$. Since $\mathbf{p} = h(\boldsymbol{\ell} + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{d})$, $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{f}|_{\mathcal{B}_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+\mathbf{d}}}$ and $\mathbf{f} = [F(h\mathbf{j})]_{\mathbf{j} \in \mathbb{Z}^2}$ we can look at

$$g_C : \mathbb{R} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad g_C(h) := \Psi_C(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p}) = \sum_{i=1}^8 a_i^C F(h[\mathcal{B}_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+\mathbf{d}}]_i) - F(\mathbf{p}), \quad C \in \{N, S, W, E, K, B\},$$

where \mathbf{a}^C are the coefficients for the linear rule Ψ_C and $[\mathcal{B}_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+\mathbf{d}}]_i$ is the i -th element of $\mathcal{B}_{2\boldsymbol{\ell}+\mathbf{d}}$ in (2). Next, on the one hand, by computing the Taylor expansion we see that

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_K(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p}) &= \frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(\mathbf{p}) h^2 + \mathcal{O}(h^4) \\ \Psi_N(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p}) &= - \left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^3}(\mathbf{p}) \right) h^3 + \mathcal{O}(h^4) \\ \Psi_S(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p}) &= \left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^3}(\mathbf{p}) \right) h^3 + \mathcal{O}(h^4) \\ \Psi_W(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p}) &= \left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x \partial y^2}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^3}(\mathbf{p}) \right) h^3 + \mathcal{O}(h^4) \\ \Psi_E(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p}) &= - \left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x \partial y^2}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^3}(\mathbf{p}) \right) h^3 + \mathcal{O}(h^4) \\ \Psi_B(\mathbf{z}) - F(\mathbf{p}) &= - \left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^3 \partial y}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{9}{16} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^4}(\mathbf{p}) \right) h^4 + \mathcal{O}(h^6), \end{aligned} \quad (80)$$

On the other hand, using a Taylor's remainder formula, we know that for each $h > 0$, $\mathbf{p} = h(\boldsymbol{\ell} + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{d})$ and $r_C \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists $\xi_C \in (0, h)$ such that

$$g_C(h) = \sum_{k=0}^{r_C-1} \frac{g_C^{(k)}(0)}{k!} h^k + \frac{g_C^{(r_C)}(\xi_C)}{r_C!} h^{r_C}, \quad C \in \{N, S, W, E, K, B\}.$$

Then, we conclude that

$$g_C(h) = \frac{g_C^{(r_C)}(\xi_C)}{r_C!} h^{r_C}, \quad C \in \{N, S, W, E, K, B\},$$

for

$$r_K = 2, \quad r_N = 3, \quad r_S = 3, \quad r_W = 3, \quad r_E = 3, \quad r_B = 4.$$

Now, we use the fact that the derivative $g_C^{(r_C)}(\xi_C)$ is a linear combination of partial derivatives of F up to order r_C evaluated at grid points, and that these derivatives are Lipschitz and bounded in modulus by a constant. Combining all these considerations we conclude the existence of $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$ fulfilling (64) and therefore prove the first part of the claim.

To prove the rest, as before, we consider $\tilde{g}_C(h) := (\mathcal{G}_C \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})$ as a function of h and write its Taylor expansion

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{G}_N \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}) &= -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(\mathbf{p})h^2 - \left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^3}(\mathbf{p}) \right) h^3 + \mathcal{O}(h^4), \\ (\mathcal{G}_S \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}) &= -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(\mathbf{p})h^2 + \left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^3}(\mathbf{p}) \right) h^3 + \mathcal{O}(h^4), \\ (\mathcal{G}_W \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}) &= -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(\mathbf{p})h^2 + \left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x \partial y^2}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^3}(\mathbf{p}) \right) h^3 + \mathcal{O}(h^4), \\ (\mathcal{G}_E \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}) &= -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(\mathbf{p})h^2 - \left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x \partial y^2}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^3}(\mathbf{p}) \right) h^3 + \mathcal{O}(h^4), \end{aligned}$$

or, equivalently, that

$$(\mathcal{G}_C \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}) = -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(\mathbf{p})h^2 + \mathcal{O}(h^3) \quad \text{for } C \in \{N, S, W, E\}.$$

As before, we can use a Taylor's remainder theorem to write

$$\tilde{g}_C(h) = \tilde{g}_C(0) + \tilde{g}_C^{(1)}(0)h + \frac{\tilde{g}_C^{(2)}(\tilde{\xi}_C)}{2}h^2 = \frac{\tilde{g}_C^{(2)}(\tilde{\xi}_C)}{2}h^2, \quad \tilde{\xi}_C \in [0, h], \quad C \in \{N, S, W, E, K, B\}.$$

Since the second partial derivatives of F are Lipschitz, then

$$\left| \tilde{g}_C^{(2)}(\tilde{\xi}_C) - \tilde{g}_C^{(2)}(0) \right| = \left| \tilde{g}_C^{(2)}(\tilde{\xi}_C) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(\mathbf{p}) \right| = \left| \tilde{g}_C^{(2)}(\tilde{\xi}_C) - \tilde{g}_C^{(2)}(0) \right| \leq M_3 |\tilde{\xi}_C - 0| \leq M_3 h,$$

where M_3 only depends on σ' , the bound of the partial derivatives up to fourth order. Therefore,

$$\tilde{g}_C^{(2)}(\tilde{\xi}_C) \leq \left| \tilde{g}_C^{(2)}(\tilde{\xi}_C) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(\mathbf{p}) \right| - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(\mathbf{p}) \leq M_3 h - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(\mathbf{p}) \leq M_3 h - \frac{1}{2} \sigma.$$

Thus, for $h < \frac{\sigma}{2M_3}$,

$$(\mathcal{G}_C \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}) = \tilde{g}_C(h) = \frac{\tilde{g}_C^{(2)}(\tilde{\xi}_C)}{2}h^2 \leq \frac{(M_3 h - \frac{1}{2} \sigma)h^2}{2} < 0.$$

Finally, computing

$$1 - \frac{(\mathcal{G}_S \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})}{(\mathcal{G}_N \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})} = \frac{(\mathcal{G}_N \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z}) - (\mathcal{G}_S \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})}{(\mathcal{G}_N \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})} = \frac{-\left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y}(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{3}{4} \frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial x^3}(\mathbf{p}) \right) h^3 + \mathcal{O}(h^4)}{-\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}(\mathbf{p})h^2 + \mathcal{O}(h^3)},$$

and using an analogous argument as before, we can find $M_1 > 0$ and $h_1 > 0$, depending on σ, σ' , such that

$$\left| 1 - \frac{(\mathcal{G}_S \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})}{(\mathcal{G}_N \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})} \right| \leq M_1 h, \quad \text{for } h < h_1.$$

In a similar way, we conclude that there exists $M_2 > 0$ and $h_2 > 0$ such that $\left| 1 - \frac{(\mathcal{G}_E \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})}{(\mathcal{G}_W \circ \Delta^{\mathcal{B}})(\mathbf{z})} \right| \leq M_2 h$, for $h < h_2$. In conclusion, both inequalities hold true for $M = \max\{M_1, M_2\}$ and $h'_0 = \min\{h_1, h_2\}$. \square